
A Study of Urban Growth in Malkapur Town of Karad Tehsil: A Geographical Analysis

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Abstract:

*Urban growth denotes the increase in the population of a specific town or city. Through the study of the urban growth, we can easily comprehend the development trajectory of a city. This understanding can facilitate the identification of developmental opportunities and the implementation of relevant projects. The primary objective of the research paper is to conduct a temporal analysis of urban growth within the Malkapur city of Karad tehsil. Numerous factors contribute to the escalating population of Malkapur, including the 24*7 water supply and the strategic positioning of the national highway traversing the town. notably, Malkapur was elevated from a gram panchayat to Nagar panchayat in 2008. renowned as a three-star town. Malkapur has witnessed a more rapid pace of development compared to both the state of Maharashtra and the nation as whole.*

Keywords: Urban Growth, Malkapur Town, Development, Temporal Analysis, Population.

Introduction:

The population is growing rapidly as people migrate from rural to urban areas in search of employment and to meet daily needs. This migration leads to the expansion of urban areas, a process known as urbanization. Since independence, the population has increased significantly, making the study of urban growth a key aspect of urban geography.

Urban studies are essential to understand ongoing development and identify the needs required to fulfil the demands of a growing population. Urbanization involves analysing factors such as urban growth and decadal population trends, which are critical for planning and development.

Several factors directly or indirectly contribute to urban growth, including:

1. Suitable Climate
2. Reliable Water Supply
3. Economic Activities

4. Availability of Land

5. Accessibility

These factors play a vital role in the development and expansion of urban areas.

Objectives:

1. To analyse the urban growth of Malkapur town in Karad tehsil.
2. To examine the population dynamics of Malkapur town.
3. To study the population trends over time.

Methodology:

This study is primarily based on secondary data obtained from the Census of India and the District Census Handbook. The data spans the period from 1961 to 2011. Percentages have been used for data analysis, and graphs and tables have been incorporated wherever applicable to present the information effectively.

Study Area:

Malkapur is a prominent town located near Karad city and is well-known within the Karad tehsil of Satara district. While Karad is a densely populated city and tehsil, Malkapur also has a significant population. The town is rich in historical significance, with the famous Agashive Caves dating back to the Gautam Buddha era. The nearby mountain hill resembles the Sanskrit symbol 'Om,' adding to its cultural importance.

Malkapur benefits from highly fertile black soil, abundant water resources from the Krushna and Koyna rivers, moderate to high rainfall, and a favourable climate, all of which contribute to its rapid population growth.

The town is also a hub for medical facilities, hosting numerous hospitals, industries, and educational institutions, attracting migrants from nearby rural areas. As of the latest count, Malkapur has a population of 31,671, with 16,352 males and 15,319 females, resulting in a sex ratio of 937 females per 1,000 males. The town is divided into 17 wards.

Malkapur is further distinguished by its 24/7 filtered water supply and its strategic location, with a national highway passing through the middle of the town. Its rapid growth can also be attributed to repeated flooding in Karad city and limited space for development in the Karad region, prompting many people to settle in Malkapur.

Table No.1: Growth of population of Malkapur town

Sr.No.	Year	Population	Decadal variation	Growth of population in percentage
1	1961	2081	-	-
2	1971	3758	+1677	44.62
3	1981	3774	+16	0.42
4	1991	5976	+2202	36.84
5	2001	22392	+16419	73.32
6	2011	31671	+9276	29.28

Table 1 highlights the urban growth of Malkapur town. In 1961, Malkapur was a village governed by a gram panchayat. Between 1961 and 1991, the population grew steadily, reaching 22,392 by 1991.

A significant surge in population occurred in 2001, with an impressive 73% increase.

This rapid growth was largely attributed to migration caused by natural calamities like floods, as people moved to Malkapur seeking safety and stability. In 2008, the town was officially upgraded to a municipal council, marking a key milestone in its urban development.

Table No.2: Work Participation

Category	Person	MALE	FEMALE
TOTAL WORKER	10887	8344	2543
A) MAIN WORKER	10181	7951	2230
1)Cultivator	736	621	115
2)Agriculture labourer	540	257	283
3)House hold industry workers	283	194	89
4)Other workers	8622	6879	1743
B) Marginal workers	706	393	313
1)Cultivators	21	14	7
2)agriculture labourers	86	37	49
3)household industries workers	51	30	21
4)other workers	548	312	236
C)NON-Workers	20784	8008	12776

Source: district census handbook, Satara.2011

Table 2 highlights the work participation in Malkapur town as per the 2011 Census. A total of 10,887 individuals are engaged in various economic activities, classified into two categories:1. Main Workers 2. Marginal Workers. In contrast,

the non-worker group, which includes individuals who do not earn money directly, such as children, homemakers, people with disabilities, senior citizens, and college students, is significantly larger, with a total of 20,784 individuals.

Table No. 3: Literacy

Sr. No.	Total	Percentage	male	Percentage of male	Female	Percentage
Literate	24762	78.18	13350	81.64	11412	74.49
Illiterate	6909	21.81	3002	18.35	3907	25.50
TOTAL	31671	100	16352	100	15319	100

Source: district census handbook, Satara.2011

Table 3 presents the total literacy rate in Malkapur town as per the 2011 Census. The overall average literacy rate, combining both males and females, is 78.18%. Among the literate population, 13,350 are males, with a literacy rate of 81.64%, and 11,412 are females, with a literacy rate of 74.49%. On the other hand, 21.81% of the total population is illiterate. This includes 3,002 illiterate males and 3,907 illiterate females.

Discussion:

Malkapur town has experienced significant growth compared to Karad, Satara, and other parts of Maharashtra. Several factors have contributed to this development:

1. Fertile Soil and Favourable Climate: Malkapur benefits from fertile soil and a favourable climate, making it an attractive location for agriculture and related activities.

2. Transportation and Accessibility: The town has a well-developed transportation network, including dense road and rail connectivity, ensuring smooth accessibility, and boosting economic activities.

3. Migration from Karad: Repeated natural calamities, especially floods, in Karad city have led many residents to relocate to Malkapur, further increasing its population and infrastructure.

4. Advanced Medical Services: Malkapur offers excellent medical facilities, with institutions like the Krushna Medical Institute providing high-quality healthcare at affordable rates for middle-class families. The town also hosts numerous multi-specialty hospitals equipped with advanced medical instruments.

5. 24/7 Water Supply: The Malkapur Municipal Council ensures a continuous

supply of clean water, enhancing the quality of life for residents.

These factors collectively contribute to Malkapur's rapid growth and increasing prominence in the region

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